

AN EFFICIENT DETECTION APPROACH OF DRIVER- DROWSINESS USING MULTIPLE CONVOLUTIONAL HAAR CASCADE KERNELIZED CNN (MCHC-KCNN) ALGORITHM

Arju Bano¹, Akash Saxena² and Gaurav K.R. Das³

Department of Computer Science and Engineering, Compucom Institute of Technology and Management, India

Abstract

A lot of detail is transmitted by the face, an essential part of the body. If there is a car in a facial movement, for example, the frequency of yawning and blinking is distinct from that of fatigue state. It's in its natural state. We suggest a new system to determine the standard of the driver. Centered on face monitoring and facial main point identification of fatigue. We are developing a new algorithm and proposing the Kernelized Convolutional Neural Network Multiple Convolutional Haar Cascade (MCHC-KCNN) Algorithm for monitoring the face of the driver using CNN and MCHC and give 0.9827 accuracy to boost the original algorithm previously proposed algorithm. Haar-feature is similar to CNN kernel, except that values of a kernel in a CNN are defined by training, and Haar-feature is determined manually. We studied the fundamentals of face detecting and eye recognition with Haar Feature-based Cascade Classifiers in this article. At first, the algorithm requires a lot of good images (faces) and poor images (face-free images) to train the classification process. Then we must remove from it some features. Haar features seen in the image below are utilized for this purpose. They are just like our convolutional kernel which gives 0.9827 accuracy i.e. efficient and more than the previous approach. We have improved our model by employing an efficient optimizer, loss function and layers, which optimizes the algorithm in a complex setting, as low light, to enhance the latter's efficiency.

Keywords:

Face Tracking, Convolutional Neural Multiple Convolutional Haar Cascade, Haar Feature-Based Cascade Classifiers, Deep Learning, Deep Neural Network

1. INTRODUCTION

In the last two years, the elimination of road injuries has not changed significantly. The key one being the driver's exhaustion and drowsy state, among the different causes. The decision-making ability of the driver to manage the vehicle thereby decreases. Symptoms of drowsiness include difficulties with focus, frequent blinking of the eye, daydreaming, missing traffic signs, repeated boredom, and so on. Furthermore, in [1], drivers who are deprived of sleep for over 4 hours are 10.2 times more probable to have accidents. As per data [2] [3]. The sleepiness of the driver is a major factor in many road accidents. As per National Sleep Foundation, approximately 51% of drivers who have driven vehicles to feel drowsy, and 17% sleep behind wheels which causes up to 100,000 crashes is associated with annual drowsiness and sleepiness over 1,500 fatalities. Driving is challenging for perceptual, distinct cognitive, motor, and decision-making capabilities. Driving capacity minimizes to 50% if sleep loss reduces attention or alertness. The driver and other road users must be safe to maintain an adequate alertness level. To increase safety on roads and highways it was reported that the drowsiness of drivers kills 1,500 people and leaves 71,000 people

hurt in road accidents annually, minimizing the sleepy driving problem is important. According to the Australian survey, around 20% of serious road accidents and 30% of fatal accidents include mistakes by driving. In comparison, a Norway study [4] shows that 3.9% of sleep-related accidents and almost 20% of night-time accidents contained DD. So, it must provide an added security feature for advising the sleepy driver who will handle the supplementary work with the hand gesture in the next set of cars coming out on the market. Such a framework may be built using multiple intrusive or non-intrusive approaches. Intrusive one takes into consideration biological parameters like EEG (Electroencephalogram), ECG (Electrocardiogram) however this technique needs electrodes to be associated with the driver's body. As it is generally costly and will annoy the driver, the drivers don't like it much. The non-intrusive method may be depended on vehicles like road location, steering wheel movement, or behavior based on, eye- blink, yawning, etc. But since the methods of driving rely on the driver's abilities and on the type of road the car is using, it is impossible to establish standardized rules. The non-contact approach has been widely used to detect fatigue due to its simple implementation and low cost. For e.g. Attention Technologies and Smart Eye [5] use driver's eyes movement and driver's head position to assess fatigue level. Several methods to measure DD have been implemented. The methods can be divided into three types:

- Driving pattern of vehicle
- Driver's psycho physiological features
- Driver monitoring computer vision techniques.

1.1 CONVENTIONAL APPROACHES FOR DROWSINESS DETECTION

The driven pattern will decide a steering wheel movement or a distance from the lane or lateral position. To keep a car on a given lane, micro-adjustment to the steering wheel is required. In drowsiness detection [6] reached an accuracy of 86% depending on the correlation between micro-adaptation and drowsiness. The deviation in lane position is utilized in another instance of driving pattern recognition. This monitors the position of the car and evaluates the deviation [7] accordingly. However, driving skills, road conditions and vehicle characteristics are highly dependent on driving patterns. Data from physiological sensors like EEG, ECG and EOG data were applied for the second class of techniques. EEG signals provide brain activity information. The Alpha, Delta and Theta signals are 3key signals in EEG to test DD. If a driver is drowsy, delta and theta signs increase slightly, alpha signals increase.

In [8] all three methods are best effective for this technique (more than 90%). The biggest drawback to this technique however is the intrusion that disrupts drivers by connecting a vast

number of sensors on the body. There are non-intrusive bio-signal approaches, but they are less precise. It is focused on the retrieval of facial features with computer vision, in which behaviors like eye closure, head movement, yawning, gaze, or facial expression are applied. In [9] applied eyelid gap to measure three levels of drowsiness. The difference was made depending on the number of blinks per minute, suggesting that the number grows as the individual develops drowsy. In [9], mouth and yawning action were taken as a drowsiness measure when Viola-Jones objected to the modification

1.2 DROWSINESS DETECTION USING DEEP LEARNING

DL has been broadly applied recently to overcome problematic issues that cannot be properly solved using conventional methods. DL focused on the CNNs makes an important breakthrough for computer vision tasks including classification of images object recognition, emotion recognition, scene segmentation in general. Dwivedi *et al.* [10] have implemented the best CNN of 78% for the detection of a drowsy driver. As the most recent investigation,

Park *et al.* [11] suggested three networks for modern architecture. AlexNet composed of 5 CNNs and 3 layer FC [12] is the first network to learn the image functionality. 16-layer VGG-FaceNet [13] is used in the second network to extract facial features. Using Flow ImageNet, the last network extracts computation features [14].

The paper is planned as follows: in section 2, we present connected work. Section 3 provided a summary of the proposed methodology describes a methodology for the Multiple Convolutional Haar Cascade (MCHC-KCNN) Algorithm. Section 4 experiment result of proposed MCHC- KCNN approach. Section 5 draws some conclusions and section 6 discusses our future work.

2. LITERATURE SURVEY

A large amount of work has now been done on the detection of drowsiness. But only a few relevant and important works of literature are described here. We review the preceding methods to DD in this chapter. Various methods were proposed to improve the accuracy and speed of DD. Conventional approaches to the detection of drowsiness and the new approaches of deep learning are listed. In this segment, we divide the associated work into three sections, those concerned with the algorithm for visual object detection, the facial algorithm the detection algorithm of landmarks, and others for the methods of Detecting Driver-Drowsiness.

Jabbar *et al.* [15] based on the detection via neural network-based methodologies of micro sleep including drowsiness. Their prior work in this area consisted of using multi-layer perceptron machine learning to detect it. This paper improves accuracy by the use of face marks observed by a camera and forwarded on to a CNN for drowsiness identification. With this work, more than 88% of the categories without glasses, over 85% in the category of the night without glasses, and lightweight substitutes to heavier classification models are achieved. In all categories, on average, more than 83% is achieved. Novel future model, as contrasted to benchmark model with a limit of 75 KB, is significantly reduced

in size, complexity as well as storage. The suggested CNN dependent model can be applied to construct an embedded system including Android devices with high accuracy and ease of usage with a real-time driver drowsiness detection system. A sleepy driver is probably a lot more dangerous on the road, as he's a victim of micro sleeps. Automotive scientists and designers are trying to solve this issue with different technical solutions to prevent such a disaster.

Kongcharoen *et al.* [16] 3-driver eye recognition algorithms have been evaluated to be implemented in Open Source approach for wake drivers, when they start to dose off (1) CNN by Haar Cascade, (2) 68 facial landmarks and (3) three-fold facial detection, with and without glasses, on both including day-night drive conditions, of this modular unit were 100 times tested. This algorithm is then tested using light (day and night), face angle (left, center and right), camera angle (left and right), and glasses (on and off), to detect both blinks and closed eyes. The outcomes show that the most effective eye detection method is CNN with a 94% Haar Cascade algorithm. The system detects drivers' eye status during driving and sounds an alert to wake the driver and stop the accident if drivers shut their eyes longer than 2 seconds. The proposed Open-source system costs approximately US\$100 and could be commonly used to help decrease road accidents worldwide. Dozing off of drivers is a leading cause of road accidents that lead to injury and death. A new open-source IoT framework was developed with this study eye-tracking.

Saltillo *et al.* [17] car driving is a dynamic and potentially risky task in the daily life of people and involves the complete participation of physiological and cognitive resources. Any lack of these means may cause accidents in traffic. The capability to adapt, prevent and react to unpredicted events, like drowsy driving. ADAS, which can inform the driver if sleepiness is perceived, is a solution to this issue. To better understand, assess and monitor human behavior in different scenarios, they can provide a driver monitoring system (DMS). The goal of this article is to detect driver drowsiness by non-intrusive measures like the behavioral solution, which is the safest way to make use of the vehicle model. The built system facilitates the retrieval of drowsiness-related measures by a typical camera study of the driver's face. First, the driver's face in a video frame is identified by a facial recognition stage. Then, there are a variety of facial landmarks. These landmarks are used to estimate the position of the head and detect the presence of a blink. DDS are observed by a Fuzzy Inference System (FIS), by monitoring correctly described ocular variables.

Deng *et al.* [18] the face, more information is contained in a substantial portion of the body. If the driver is under stress, facial expressions, e.g. duration of the blinking and yawning, are diverse. In this paper, they propose a DriCare, approach whereby drivers are identified with video images without using devices like yawning, blinking, and closure of the eyes. They incorporate a new face-tracking algorithm to improve the tracking precision due to the constraints of previous algorithms. A novel facial region detector has also been established depended on 68 key points. They then measure the driver's situation using these facial areas. By combining eye and mouth features, DriCare alerts the driver to fatigue. Experimental studies have shown DriCare to be 92% accuracy.

Yu et al. [19] give drowsy detection, mobile real-time DDD application. The following steps are included in Drowsy Detection. First, facial areas and landmarks are obtained using a model and a reference model for facial detection. Second, 3-NN models are developed to classify the state of facial drowsiness, the state of eyes and mouth. Lastly, the condition of drivers is obtained based on outcomes of all model models (i.e. normal, yawning and sleep). Both models are lightweight, mobile phone-enabled CNN models. Drowsy Detection is not intrusive relative to current approaches, since mobile phone without Internet is required only. They make a large drowsiness dataset for drivers to test our method including various genders, ages, head locations and light. Experimental findings indicate that Drowsy Detection can reach an average of 97.8 million with significantly high accuracy. Day by day, the number of driving accidents are growing, and drowsiness is a cause of road accidents. Drowsiness detection research is critical to increasing the safety of road traffic. Most conventional ways are however invasive because often costly sensors are required. Also, they perform only when only single features and superficial classifiers are adopted.

Mehta et al. [20] an advanced system called AD3S (Advanced DDD System) has been proposed using Android. The machine records the drivers' facial features in real-time. The facial marks are often used to measure other parameters, including the Eye Aspect Ratio and Nose Length Ratio, based on adaptive levels that detect drowsiness by the driver. AD3S has a non-intrusive design and is non-intrusive efficient. Machine learning and in-deep learning methods were used over 1200 application users for evaluating the performance of AD3S. The analytical findings indicate that future techniques can detect driver drowsiness with accuracy in the bagging classification of around 98 percent. The drowsiness of drivers is a major cause of road injuries worldwide. Long-lasting, monotonous, impatient driving leads to somnolence and fatal accidents. A large number of road accidents can be evaded by the automatic identification of DD.

Gupta et al. [21] offers a non-solution to the implementation of an alert driver for drivers who can detect and monitor the yawning and sleepiness of driver. For face detection and recognition of facial points, the device uses a histogram-oriented gradient (HOG). SVM is then used to search for the facial or non-face object observed. EAR and MAR of the driver is monitored to control sleepiness and yawning across a set number of frames. Since drivers' drowsiness or tiredness is often dependent on the number of hours they have driven, an extra aspect is included so the eye and mouth threshold frames are different. This stimulates the machine to the detection of drowsiness. It also needs the addition of face recognition so that each driver can monitor separately. Our experimental results show that they are effective in our proposed system. The booming number of road accidents is now one of the most prevalent problems in the world. Unacceptable and unwanted driving is the biggest cause of road accidents. Drowsiness or lack of attention of the driver is considered the primary cause for such mishaps. Driver drowsiness monitoring research can help minimize accidents.

Kumar and Patra [22] gives the cause of road crashes and death is one of the main driving causes. Therefore, fatigue detection and an indication of the driver is an active field of study. Either vehicle-driven or behavioral or physiologically based is the most common method. Few solutions distract drivers; others need

expensive sensors and data processing. This research, therefore, establishes a low-cost, real-time system for the detection of drowsiness of the driver developed system usages image analysis methods to record the video and detect the driver's side on each frame. Facial features are shown on the face and eye aspect ratio, the opening of mouth and relation of nose length are measured and illness is detected based on the theoretical framework, depending on the values. Algorithms for machine learning have also been applied offline. In the SVM-based classification sensitivity of 95, 58% and 100% accuracy was achieved. [22].

Reddy et al. [23] provides status of drivers is important because drivers' inattention or drowsiness is the main reason for motor vehicle chances. Drowsiness detector on a vehicle will minimize many accidents. Owing to a single moment of negligence, accidents occur and the driver monitoring system that operates in real-time is important. This detector can be installed and operated at high accuracy on an embedded device. This paper suggests a method to have drowsiness dependent on DL, which can be applied and performed with high accuracy on a low-cost embedded board. Their paper is specifically condensing a lightweight model from a heavy baseline to an integrated board. Also, a minimized network structure has been developed to identify whether the driver is drowsy or not depended on face landmark input. In terms of 3-class rating and speed of 14.8 frames per second on Jetson TK1 proposed model achieved an accuracy of 89.5%.

Yan et al. [24] develops a grayscale image processing-based real-time DD system and PERCLOS for determining if a driver is drowsy. The method proposed consists of three parts, first of all: it calculates driver's face approximately in grayscale scale and then small template analyzing eye positions; furthermore, it usages data from preceding phase; and thirdly, it uses PERCLOS to construct an exhausted model. When the driver is exhausted, the system alerts the driver to stop and rest.

Lin et al. [25] provides the embedded system, RF system and mind wave machine, named NeuroSky, were developed in real-time. NeuroSky collects mind wave data to track the condition of the driver based on feature extraction and classification method. To minimize the rate of incidents of transport, the Rf system will transfer data to an embedded system. Quick pedestrian detection, remote control, lane output warning system and reverse image solutions are widely applied by vehicles, and in the system in past have not been applied to DDD in real-time. Biomedical signal treatment recently solved biomechanical science problems, e.g. mind-brain imaging, encephalogram, electroencephalography, successful dynamic distributed cranial nerve analyzes and more brain message processing processes. The key cause for road accidents is due to long driving drowsiness. Brain signal analysis depended on EEG could be able to predict driver drowsiness in an attempt to warn the driver.

Li et al. [26] Proposes on the SVM-based posterior probabilistic model (SVMPPM) for DDD to translate the level of drowsiness in the place of discrete labels at all levels of 0~1. To assess the proposed model in real-time, fully wearable EEG device consisting of a Bluetooth-enabled EEG headband and the commercial smart watch was applied. This model was built with 20 individuals involved in a 1-hour monotonous voice driving simulation research, 15 subjects for the structure model and 5 subjects for the research model. Video reference suggests that, for

an alert group (73 out of 80 datasets), the proposed system achieved a precision of 91.25%; for an early-warning group (93 out of 111 data sets) 83.78%; and for full-warning group 91.92% (91 out of 99 data sets). Hydride of proposed SVM ,PPM, EEG Headband and smart device with wrist- consuming results shows a wearable solution that is operative, simple and inexpensive for DDD. DD is the world's main cause of death from auto accidents. Many signs to detect driver drowsiness have been suggested. Between these signals is an EEG signal more directly related to drowsiness that indicates brain function. In recent years, however, a vast number of EEG-DDD models have gained increasing attention. However, one constraint of these experiments is that these equations simply estimate discrete marks, so the relative severity of driver drowsiness could be estimated.

3. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

In this field, we are analyzed different experimentation for Real-Time DDD System. In a practical simulation setting, we took careful care to carry out our test testing. For a practical mode of vehicular mobility. With python as a simulation tool, we analyzed our model. While certain traditional models can detect the positions of several facials, the eyes and mouth areas of the driver cannot be established. However, the driver will practically have diverse and complex facial expressions that distort their detection.

3.1 PROBLEM STATEMENT

DriCare and other existing work theoretically solve three crucial problems. Since the heights of the drivers are diverse, the places of their faces are different in the film. And, as the driver is driving, her or his head will be moving; it is, therefore, necessary to follow the head direction in time until the head location moves. This is likely unless the model begins to learn unnecessary face features. Outcomes achieve, therefore, that our optimized model for DNNs can be implemented with extreme accuracy to detect drowsiness on embedded devices.

3.2 METHODOLOGY

We use YawDD [27] dataset and volunteer video data. Firstly, we suggest a novel face-tracking algorithm called 2d CNN which optimizes the algorithm in a dynamic environment, e.g. low light, to enhance the accuracy of low light. CNN is used to evaluate the eye state. Going to improve CNN's accuracy. In this research, we use 2D-CNN for training and testing to predict the driver's drowsiness at the time of driving. The proposed model is used to tackle the irrelative prediction of classes and labels. The proposed model will improve the test and validation accuracy and reduce the overfitting problem. The problem will overcome with the help 14 layers deep neural

Network in which have 5 Conv2D layers for feature extraction from a given dataset and other layers like max-pooling, flatten, dropout, and 2 dense layers. Classification layer dense and network output labels for the proposed network final output. In their 2001 paper, Rapid Object Detection with Boosted Cascade of Simple Features, Paul Viola and Michael Jones proposed an efficient object detection technique by using hair feature-based cascades classifiers. It's an ML that trains a cascade from many good and evil images. It is applied for detecting objects in other

images. We focus on facial recognition here. To train the classifier, an algorithm first requires many positive (face-images) and negative images. Each kernel now has all possible sizes and positions to measure several characteristics. (Imagine exactly how much computation is essential? There are also 160000 features in a 24×24 window). The sum of pixels in white and black rectangles must be recognized for every feature calculation. They presented the whole image to solve this. As big as your image, designs for a certain pixel are simplified to an operation with only four pixels. Nice, right, isn't it? Nice? It does things very quickly. Even so, most of the characteristics we calculated are irrelevant. The deliberate image below, for example. Two good features rank in the top row. The first characteristic chosen seems to reflect on a feature that the eye area is frequently darker than the nose and cheeks region. 2nd feature selected is that the eyes are darker than the nose bridge. So, we have used MCHC-KCNN and we improved the model for enhancing accuracy. The model information is described following.

3.3 MODEL DETAILS

In this model, we use the following layers, activation function, loss function, and optimizer

- **Model:** Sequential
- **Feature Extraction Layer**→Conv2Dconvolution 2D layer
- **Pooling layer** → *MaxPooling2D*: Maximum value per patch or feature map. Maximum pooling (or Max pooling).
- **Flatten layer:** Flattening converts the data to the next layer for input to a 1- dimensional array.
- **Dropout layer:** Dropout applies to the input. The drop-out layer sets out input units randomly at a rate of 0, per step in training, to avoid overfitting. Inputs not set to 0 have been reduced to $1/(1-rate)$, so the sum for all inputs does not change.
- **Dense Layer:** A dense layer is a regular NN layer that is deeply connected. The layer is frequently and most widely used. The following procedure is performed by the dense layer on the input and returns the output.
- **Loss function (categorical cross entropy):** Produces a single-hot array with the possible match of each category.
- **Optimizer:** Adam Optimization is a stochastic gradient descent approach based on a first-order and second-order adaptive estimate of moments. The method is computationally efficient, has a low memory requirement and invariant for diagonal gradient rescaling, according to Kingma et al. 2014, and is well suited to problems with high data/parameters.

4. MCHC-KCNN

- Step 1:** Face recognizes using get frontal face to detect the face
- Step 2:** Apply face predictor shape 68 predictors for face feature detection for cross-checking
- Step 3:** Apply eye and mouth aspect ratio (EAR and MAR)
- Step 4:** Apply Haar Cascade for classifying negative and positive images

Step 5: For feature, extraction applies Haar Cascade over the dataset to detect the face features present in images

Step 6: Step to train a neural network Step7: Prediction

Fig.1. Flowchart of Proposed Work

The Fig.1 shows the flow chart of the proposed methodology. We apply methods Multiple Convolutional Haar Cascade Kernelized Convolutional Neutral Network (MCHC-KCNN). Our architecture analyzes and detects driver state using each frame image. The eyes and mouth of the driver play a key role in tracking. Consequently, the driver needs to evaluate fatigue in the main facial features. The quality of the images is affected during the detection process and the human face does not know if there is a difference in the illumination intensity of the cab. This usually happens when the skylights, rain, and the night are overcast. We use illumination enhancements for preprocessing images before tracking the driver's face for detection accuracy. This flow chart shows what we are suggesting. Haar feature is the same as a kernel in CNN, except that values of a kernel in a CNN are calculated by training, whereas a Haar-Feature is determined by hand.

The proposed model architecture includes a standalone convolution layer (conv2D-1, conv2D- 2, conv2D-3, conv2D-4, conv2D-5), 5 max-pooling layers, and a final output layer (DL2). Because of its extreme accuracy, CNNs are used for the classification and recognition of images. There was an error. The CNN occurs a hierarchical model which acts similar funnel on the creation of network and produces a completely connected layer where all neurons are linked and output managed. To this end, the Cascade of Classifiers definition was introduced. The functions are classified into various classification classes and are independently implemented instead of all 6000 functions in a window. In the first few measures, typically, certain features are less visible. If the first move fails, discard it. The other features on it are not considered. Using the second feature stage, and continue the process as it passes. The all-stage window is a facing

region. However, because the Haar Features must be manually defined, the types of items it can detect have some limit. If we give the edge and line features of a classifier (a network, or an algorithm detecting faces), so objects with simple edges and lines can only be identified. Even as a face detector, The Haar-classifier cannot recognize the face, if we interfere with the face a little (say, cover the eyes with sunglasses, or turn the head to the side). In comparison, a convolutional kernel has a larger degree of independence (because training is determined) and can identify partly covered faces (depending on training data quality).

5. EXPERIMENTAND DISCUSSION

In this section, we have experimented with the proposed approach using Multiple Convolutional Haar Cascade Kernelized Convolutional Neutral Network (MCHC-KCNN). We use 2D-CNN for training and testing to predict the driver's drowsiness at the time of driving. The proposed model is used to tackle the irrelative prediction of classes and labels. The proposed model will improve the test and validation accuracy and reduce the overfitting problem. The problem will overcome with the help 14 layers deep neural network in which have 5 Conv2D layers for feature extraction from a given dataset and other layers like carpooling, flatten, dropout, and 2 dense layers. Dense layer use for classify and labels for network final output of the proposed network.

Fig.2. Graph of Training and testing Accuracy

The Fig.2 shows that the results of Training and testing accuracy our system offers the best accuracy which increases efficiency in which accuracy is 0.9827 and validation accuracy is 0. 9696.

Fig.3. Training and Testing Loss

We have used the 20:80 ratios for training and testing, the driver wears no glasses while the cab is bright. The accuracy of the fatigue motion is decreased when the driver wearing a lightly low glass and driving atmosphere. For the present time, the reliability of our system cannot be measured by a public image driver drowsiness recognition data set.

The Fig.3 shows the results of Training and Testing Loss. On the training data, our model does better than on the unknown date of validation. It may also occur if our learning loss is calculated as an average moving over 1 epoch, while the validation loss is calculated after the same study epoch. In this work, the loss is 0.0619, and the validation loss is 0.1032.

Table.1. Classification report of MCHC-KCNN

Label	Precision	Recall	F1-Score	Support
Yawn	0.56	0.91	0.69	53
No yawn	0.77	0.52	0.62	65
Closed	0.99	0.80	0.88	187
Open	0.88	0.99	0.93	188
Accuracy	0.98	0.96	0.85	493
Macro average	0.80	0.81	0.78	493
Weighted average	0.87	0.85	0.85	493

The Table.1 shows the classification Report of the proposed Multiple Convolutional Haar Cascade Kernelized Convolutional Neural Network (MCHC-KCNN). All we have to do is training the weightings of every feature (that is, more Haar-feature) so that we can train classifier well deprived of many training images. Furthermore, it often operates more efficiently, as Haar classifiers usually need less computations. Team then formed its individual CNN to identify emotion on the face after finding faces. The above result efficient than the previous approach.

6. CONCLUSION

We suggest a new system to determine the standard of the driver. Centered on face monitoring and facial main point identification of fatigue. We are developing a new algorithm and proposing the MCHC-KCNN Algorithm for monitoring the face of the driver using CNN and MCHC and give 0.9827 accuracy to boost the original algorithm previously proposed algorithm. Haar-Feature is similar to a kernel in CNN, except a CNN determines kernel values by training, though Haar-Feature is physically determined. We are describing facial main points-based identification zones. We, moreover, introduce a new Sleepiness Appraisal Approach depends upon a state of eyes and mouth. We have improved our model by employing an efficient Optimizer, loss function, and layers which optimizes the algorithm in a complex setting, like low light, to enhance the latter's efficiency. we utilize CNN to evaluate the state of the eye. Toward enhance the accuracy of CNN.

6.1 FUTURE SCOPE

In future work, by real driving experiments, we can further improve the reliable and applicable drowsiness detection systems. Our analysis was focused on the behavior of the driver that has improved the driver's posture for some time. If the driver is

drowsy and does not change his position, this method is reduced. Our approach is not able to predict this particular case but may improve by driver physiology. An infrared camera can also be applied as future work to capture driver conducts at night. Also, a casual hear-rate sensor and image sensor can be studied as a multimodal DL method and more new models can be modified to minimize runtime by adapting compression and knowledge distillation techniques.

REFERENCES

- [1] Pushpa Narayan, "IIT-M's Wake Up Call for Tired Drivers", Available at: <https://timesofindia.indiatimes.com/city/chennai/IIT-Ms-wake-up-callfor-tired-drivers/articleshow/28869401.cms>, Accessed at 2014.
- [2] B. Verma and A. Choudhary, "Framework for Dynamic Hand Gesture Recognition using Grassmann Manifold for Intelligent Vehicles", *IET Intelligent Transport Systems*, Vol. 17, No. 3, pp. 124-134, 2018
- [3] The Royal Society for the Prevention of Accident, "Driver Fatigue and Road Accidents", Available at: <https://www.rospa.com/rospaweb/docs/advice-services/road-safety/drivers/fatigue-litreview.pdf>, Accessed at 2001.
- [4] B. Verma, and A. Choudhary, "Unsupervised Learning-Based Static Hand Gesture Recognition from RGB-D Sensor", *Proceedings of International Conference on Soft Computing and Pattern Recognition*, pp. 304-314, 2016.
- [5] Smart Eye, "Smart Eye", Available at: <https://smarteeye.se/>, Accessed at 2018.
- [6] J. Krajewski, D. Sommer, U. Trutschel, D. Edwards and M. Golz, "Steering Wheel Behavior-Based Estimation of Fatigue", *Proceedings of International Driving Symposium on Human Factors in Driver Assessment, Training and Vehicle Design*, pp. 118-124, 2017.
- [7] Driver Alert Control (DAC), Available at: <http://support.volvocars.com/uk/cars/Pages/owners-manual.aspx?mc=Y555&my=2015&sw=14w20&article=2e82f6fc0d1139c2c0a801e800329d4e>, Accessed at 2016.
- [8] Z. Mardi, S.N. Ashtiani and M. Mikaili, "EEG-Based Drowsiness Detection for Safe Driving using Chaotic Features and Statistical Tests", *Journal of Medical Signals and Sensors*, Vol. 1, No. 2, pp. 130-137, 2011.
- [9] B. Hariri, S. Abtahi, S. Shirmohammadi and L. Martel, "A Yawning Measurement Method to Detect Driver Drowsiness", *Proceedings of International Conference on Instrumentation and Measurement Technology*, pp. 1-14, 2011.
- [10] K. Dwivedi, K. Biswaranjan and A. Sethi, "Drowsy Driver Detection using Representation Learning", *Proceedings of International Conference on Advance Computing*, pp. 21-24, 2014.
- [11] S. Park, F. Pan, S. Kang and C.D. Yoo, "Driver Drowsiness Detection System based on Feature Representation Learning using Various Deep Networks", *Proceedings of ACCV Workshop on Driver Drowsiness Detection from Video*, pp. 1-7, 2016.
- [12] A. Krizhevsky, I. Sutskever and G.E. Hinton, "Imagenet Classification with Deep Convolutional Neural Networks",

- Proceedings of International Conference on Neural Information Processing Systems*, pp. 1097-1105, 2012.
- [13] O.M. Parkhi, A. Vedaldi and A. Zisserman, "Deep Face Recognition", *Proceedings of International Conference on British Machine Vision*, pp. 1-6, 2015.
- [14] J. Donahue, L. Anne Hendricks and S. Venugopalan, "Long-Term Recurrent Convolutional Networks for Visual Recognition and Description", *Proceedings of International Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*, pp. 2625-2634, 2015.
- [15] R. Jabbar, M. Shinoy, M. Kharbeche, K. Al-Khalifa, M. Krichen and K. Barkaoui, "Driver Drowsiness Detection Model using Convolutional Neural Networks Techniques for Android Application", *Proceedings of International Conference on Informatics, IoT, and Enabling Technologies*, pp. 237-242, 2020.
- [16] W. Kongcharoen, S. Nuchitprasitchai, Y. Nilsiam and J.M. Pearce, "Real-Time Eye State Detection System for Driver Drowsiness using Convolutional Neural Network", *Proceedings of International Conference on Electrical Engineering/Electronics, Computer, Telecommunications and Information Technology*, pp. 551-554, 2020.
- [17] G. Salzillo, C. Natale, G.B. Fioccola and E. Landolfi, "Evaluation of Driver Drowsiness based on Real-Time Face Analysis", *Proceedings of International Conference on Systems, Man, and Cybernetics*, pp. 328-335, 2020.
- [18] W. Deng and R. Wu, Ruoxue, "Real-Time Driver-Drowsiness Detection System using Facial Features", *IEEE Access*, Vol. 8, pp. 1-11, 2019.
- [19] C. Yu, X. Qin, Y. Chen, J. Wang and C. Fan, "DrowsyDet: A Mobile Application for Real-time Driver Drowsiness Detection", *Proceedings of International Conference on Advanced and Trusted Computing*, pp. 321-334, 2019.
- [20] S. Mehta, P. Mishra, A.J. Bhatt and P. Agarwal, "AD3S: Advanced Driver Drowsiness Detection System using Machine Learning", *Proceedings of International Conference on Image Information Processing*, pp. 108-113, 2019.
- [21] I. Gupta, N. Garg, A. Aggarwal, N. Nepalia and B. Verma, "Real-Time Driver's Drowsiness Monitoring based on Dynamically Varying Threshold", *Proceedings of International Conference on Contemporary Computing*, pp. 1-6, 2018.
- [22] A. Kumar and R. Patra, "Driver Drowsiness Monitoring System using Visual Behaviour and Machine Learning", *Proceedings of International Conference on Computer Applications and Industrial Electronics*, pp. 339-344, 2018.
- [23] B. Reddy, Y. Kim, S. Yun, C. Seo and J. Jang, "Real-Time Driver Drowsiness Detection for Embedded System using Model Compression of Deep Neural Networks", *Proceedings of International Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*, pp. 438-445, 2017.
- [24] J. Yan, H. Kuo, Y. Lin and T. Liao, "Real-Time Driver Drowsiness Detection System Based on PERCLOS and Grayscale Image Processing", *Proceedings of International Conference on Computer, Consumer and Control*, pp. 243-246, 2016.
- [25] C. Lin, C. Ding, C. Liu and Y. Liu, "Development of a Real-Time Drowsiness Warning System based on an Embedded System", *Proceedings of International Conference on Advanced Robotics and Intelligent Systems*, pp. 1-4, 2015.
- [26] G. Li, B. Lee and W. Chung, "Smartwatch-Based Wearable EEG System for Driver Drowsiness Detection", *IEEE Sensors Journal*, Vol. 15, No. 12, pp. 7169-7180, 2015.
- [27] Shabnam Abtahi, Mona Omidyeganeh, Shervin Shirmohammadi, and Behnoosh Hariri, "Yawdd: A Yawning Detection Dataset", *Proceedings of International Conference on Multimedia Systems*, pp. 24-28, 2014.